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Research Article

**A RESEARCH STUDY TO ASSESS THE SIGNIFICANT
COMPLICATIONS AND PATTERN OF DIABETIC FOOT
DISEASE, WHICH LEADS TO AMPUTATION****¹Dr Muhammad Akhter, ²Dr Muhammad Abdullah Waqar, ³Dr Muhammad Ahsan
Akram**¹Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur.**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: Diabetic foot is a significant diabetes complication, which may also result in amputations. Therefore, our research objective is to evaluate the pattern and causes of amputations among patients of diabetes.

Subjects and Methods: We carried out this research on 1985 patients at Allied hospital Faisalabad from Jan 2018 to Dec 2018. There were 1249 males and 736 female patients in the research sample. In these patients, 1295 had experienced minor and major amputations. Data was collected on a pre-designed Performa, which collected information about amputations level, detail of deformity, diabetic history, amputations cause and related diabetic complications. Peripheral vascular disease and neuropathy were respectively evaluated by Doppler studies and 10g monofilament and tuning fork (125 Hz).

Results: Primary reason for amputations was an infection as ninety percent of patients presented infection. Among amputations, there were 918 cases of minor amputations (70.9%) and 377 of major amputations (29.1%). Patients experiencing amputations experienced 11.9% above the knee and 50% below knee amputations. More than fifty percent of amputations were of rays and toes. Claw toes, neuropathy and peripheral vascular disease occurrence were respectively 64%, 82% and 35%.

Conclusion: In the light of outcomes, it is concluded that the leading cause of amputation is an infection. Rays, toes and below knee amputations are common among reported amputations. Proper footwear selection and foot care education need more emphasis among diabetic patients.

Keywords: Neuropathy, Below Knee, Above Knee, Amputations, Major, Minor, Footwear, Rays, Toes, Foot, Diabetic, Diabetes and Vascular Disease.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus accounts for premature morbidity and mortality and affects about 35 million individuals all over the world [1 – 3]. Foot disease is one of the major complications which lead to amputations especially in the underdeveloped countries [4 – 6]. Amputations are less common in non-diabetic patients than in diabetic patients [7]. Foot ulcers produce most of the diabetes-related amputations. Foot ulcer refers to a combination of poor foot care, infection, peripheral neuropathy and peripheral vascular disease [8, 9]. The significant risk factors requiring amputation for diabetic patients require neuropathy, lower extremity ischemia, foot ulcer history, retinopathy, elevated HbA1c and its indicators include peripheral arterial occlusion, septic gangrene, severe soft tissue infection, non-healing ulcer and osteomyelitis [10, 11].

Different regions present different reasons for the occurrence of amputations. Studies show that most of the foot ulcers are related to gross infection and they are neuropathic [12, 13]. Epidemiological data shows most of the diabetes patients with limb amputations (40% – 70%). The outcomes of diabetic foot are severe as every thirty-second one leg is lost due to diabetic foot all over the world [14, 15]. Hospitalization is also increased due to foot-related complications. Forty percent of the healthcare sources have been consumed by foot issues in the underdeveloped countries [15, 16]. These amputations affect the psychosocial status and physical functioning of the patients along with prolonged hospitalization and unemployment. Diabetic foot is a significant diabetes complication which may also result in amputations. Therefore, our research objective is to evaluate the pattern and causes of amputations among patients of diabetes.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

We carried out this research on a total of 1985 patients at Allied hospital Faisalabad from Feb 2018 to Jan 2019. There were 1249 males and 736 female patients in the research sample. In these patients 1295 had experienced minor and major amputations. Data was collected on a pre-designed Proforma which collected

information about amputations level, detail of deformity, diabetic history, amputations cause and related diabetic complications. Peripheral vascular disease and neuropathy were respectively evaluated by Doppler studies and 10g monofilament and tuning fork (125 Hz). We assessed the records of different centres to identify the rate of amputations. Sources of information were limb fitting centres, hospital discharge registers and operation theatres. Patients gave their informed consent and approval of the hospital ethical committee was also taken before the commencement of research.

It was not possible to reduce foot deformity manually due to abnormal or contracture prominence. Signs of inflammation and purulent drainage presented signs of foot infection along with tenderness, warmth, redness and swelling. Major amputations were carried out at the hip, hind quarter, above the knee, below the knee, through knee or through ankle; whereas, minor amputations were carried out through metatarsal bones, tarsometatarsal joints, rays or toes. Toe amputation was carried out in the patients of gangrene restricted to toe, toe ulceration and distal osteomyelitis or septic interphalangeal joint or middle phalanx. Ray amputation was carried out among those patients who involved a necrotic process in toe base. Trans metatarsal amputation was carried out among infections of metatarsophalangeal joint or multiple toes. Statistical analysis was made on SPSS software (P-Value < 0.05).

RESULTS:

The primary reason for amputations was an infection as ninety percent patients presented infection. Among amputations, there were 918 cases of minor amputations (70.9%) and 377 of major amputations (29.1%). Patients experiencing amputations experienced 11.9% above the knee and 50% below knee amputations. More than fifty percent amputations were of rays and toes. Claw toes, neuropathy and peripheral vascular disease occurrence was respectively 64%, 82% and 35%.

Detailed outcomes are presented in the tabular and graphical data given below:

Table – I: Regions Wise Stratification

Region	Number of Centres	Diabetic Patients	Subjects with Amputations
North	3	199	127
East	4	304	215
West	3	182	113
South	21	1300	840
Total	31	1985	1295

Table – II: Gender Distribution

Diabetic Patients	Without Amputations (690)	With Amputations (1295)
Male	399	850
Female	291	445

Table – III: Demographic Information

Diabetic Patients	Without Amputations (690)		With Amputations (1295)		P-Value
	Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD	
Age (Years)	52.8	11.6	56.5	10.3	< 0.0001
DM Duration (Years)	7.7	5.9	11.9	6.4	
HbA1C (%)	8.1	0.8	9	2.1	

Table – IV: Reasons of Amputation

Reasons for Amputation	Number	Percentage
Infection	1169	90.3
Trauma	59	4.5
Frost Bite	12	0.9

Table – V: Level of Amputation

Level of Amputation	Number	Percentage
Hind quarter	26	2.00
Hip	8	0.60
Above Knee	45	3.50
Through Knee	25	1.90
Below Knee	222	17.10
Through ankle or Taurus	51	3.90
Through Tarsometatarsal joints	95	7.30
Through metatarsal Bones	108	8.30
Great toe (± other toes) or first ray	333	25.70
Other toe(s) or ray(s) (including great toe)	382	29.50

Table – VI: Type of Deformities

Deformities	Number	Percentage
Claw Toes	828	64
Osteoarthropathy	420	32.4
Nerve Thickening	12	0.92
Per Planus	6	0.46
Per Cavus	7	0.54

Table – VII: Diabetic Complications

Complications	Number
Retinopathy	34.8
Nephropathy	21.4
Neuropathy	82
CVD	24.2
CVA	4.2
PVD	35.3
Arterial Embolism	3.2

DISCUSSION:

Majority of the foot complications are infective and neuropathic than being vascular [17]. We assessed the

amputation profile among diabetes patients with the prevalent cause of amputation as an infection which accounted for ninety percent of the amputations.

Among amputations, there were 918 cases of minor amputations (70.9%) and 377 of major amputations (29.1%). Patients experiencing amputations experienced 11.9% above the knee and 50% below knee amputations. More than fifty percent amputations were of rays and toes. Claw toes, neuropathy and peripheral vascular disease occurrence were respectively 64%, 82% and 35%. A Kenyan author reported trauma as a major cause of the amputations (35.7%), which is different than out reported outcomes [18]. Ulcer development has an association with peripheral vascular disease, peripheral neuropathy, infection and foot deformity. We reported neuropathy, PVD and claw toes among 85%, 35% and 64% respectively. A Turkish author reported different amputation profile among diabetic foot cases with an overall rate of amputation (39.4%) [19]. Most applied procedures were knee amputations and ray amputation having a respective proportion of 30% and 35%.

An African study also highlighted the onset of health issues, amputation, mortality and prolonged hospitalization among patients due to diabetic foot [13, 20]. Chaturvedi reported complications among both Types – I & II diabetes patients about amputations [21]. Another series reported significantly associated factors with lower extremity and major amputations such as neuropathy, ischemia, wound depth and infection grade [22]. Better healthcare facilities may assist in order to reduce amputations significantly along with better glycemic control and spreading awareness [9, 13, 15, 23]. Simple amputations can control 80% of foot ulceration cases [24]. Footcare is crucial to control foot amputations [25]. Preventive strategies are helpful to prevent surgery and new issues among the patients of diabetic foot [26]. Educational and awareness spreading programs are also equally helpful for better foot care and selection of suitable footwear [27].

CONCLUSION:

In the light of outcomes, it is concluded that the leading cause of amputation is an infection. Rays, toes and below knee amputations are common among reported amputations. Proper footwear selection and footcare education need more emphasis among diabetic patients.

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